

Prevalence of Early Post-Thyroidectomy Complications and Associated Factors at TZNA General Hospital in Ethiopia

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ABSTRACT

Background: Thyroid gland diseases are among the most common endocrine system disorders worldwide, with goiter accounting for a significant portion. Goiter is endemic in Ethiopia and one of the leading causes of elective general surgery. Thyroidectomy is the primary treatment method for such conditions. While thyroidectomy itself rarely results in death, it is associated with several complications during the early post-operative period, which can lead to further complications and potentially death. Hence, understanding the extent and underlying causes of these complications is crucial to implementing targeted intervention. Therefore, the study aimed to determine the prevalence of early post thyroidectomy complications and associated factors at TZNA General Hospital in Addis Ababa, Ethiopia.

Methods: A retrospective chart review was conducted among 278 eligible patients who underwent thyroidectomy at the hospital between October 2016 and October 2022. Data was summarized and presented using a frequency table. To identify factors associated with early post-thyroidectomy complications, a binary logistic regression analysis was run at 5% level of significance using SPSS V.20.0 software. Adjusted odds ratio (AOR) and 95% CI for AOR were used for interpretation of significant results.

Results: The prevalence of early post-thyroidectomy complications was 43.5% (95% CI = 37.6 - 49.4). Being male (AOR=0.26, 95% CI=0.09-0.73, p=0.01) and undergoing thyroid lobectomy with isthmectomy (AOR=0.10, 95% CI=0.01-0.79, p=0.029) were found to be associated with 74% and 90% lower odds of developing complications, respectively. On the other hand, diagnosis of follicular thyroid cancer was associated with eight-fold increased odds of developing complications (AOR=7.99, 95% CI=1.22-52.0).

Conclusions: Early post-thyroidectomy complications were found to be frequent and significantly associated with gender, procedure type, and histopathology. To mitigate these risks, pre-operative assessments should identify high-risk patients, followed by tailored intraoperative measures and close monitoring with targeted interventions in post-operative care.

Key words: Post-thyroidectomy complications, Goiter, Retrospective chart review, Binary Logistic Regression, Ethiopia.

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